

Solvent Extraction of Zinc(II) with Quinaldic Acid into Benzyl Alcohol

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The role of zinc as an essential nutrient is well established¹. The ever expanding interest and applications of zinc have generated a great demand for more accurate and reliable technique for separating zinc from a variety of complex matrices. The reagent quinaldic acid² has been used for the solvent extraction of Cu^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}. However, quinaldic acid has not been used for the solvent extraction of Zn^{II}. The present work describes a method for the solvent extraction and radiochemical separation of Zn^{II} employing quinaldic acid as a reagent. ⁶⁵Zn was used as a tracer.

Results and Discussion

The extraction coefficient value revealed a maximum *E* value of 84 at a pH of 8.0. The percentage extraction was found to be greater than 98.0% in the pH range 7.0–10.0. The *E* value was found to decrease in the more acidic range (Table 1). The reproducibility of the method was found to be 6.33%. The extraction coefficient value was found to be maximum for an equilibration time of 4.0 min under the experimental conditions (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH AND TIME OF EQUILIBRATION

pH	Extraction coefficient (<i>E</i>)	Extraction %	Time of equilibration min
2.0	0.1	9.0	4.0
3.0	0.4	28.5	4.0
4.0	1.1	52.3	4.0
5.0	3.0	75.0	4.0
6.0	29.0	96.6	4.0
7.0	65.0	98.5	4.0
7.5	70.0	98.6	4.0
8.0	79.0	98.7	4.0
8.5	62.0	98.4	4.0
9.0	54.0	98.2	4.0
10.0	51.0	98.1	4.0
8.0	55.0	98.2	1.0
8.0	68.0	98.5	2.0
8.0	71.0	98.6	3.0
8.0	84.0	98.7	4.0
8.0	65.0	98.5	5.0
8.0	60.0	98.4	6.0
8.0	60.0	98.4	7.0

Of the solvents studied, the *E* value was found to be maximum for benzyl alcohol. The extraction coefficient value (*E* in parenthesis) revealed a decreasing trend: Benzyl alcohol (84) > isoamyl alcohol (39) > pentanol (30) > toluene (25) > heptanol (13) > nitromethane (1.20) > xylene (0.98) > nitrobenzene (0.87) > chloroform (0.41) > isoamyl acetate (0.20) > benzene (0.06) > methyl isobutyl

ketone (0.03) > cyclohexane (0.02) > *o*-dichlorobenzene (0.008) > heptane (0.005) > carbon tetrachloride (0.004) > hexane (0.003) = ethyl acetate (0.003). After equilibration no phase separation was observed for isopropyl alcohol, pyridine, methyl ethyl ketone, ethylene glycol, hexane and heptane.

Effect of foreign ions: The effect of sodium, potassium or ammonium salts on the extraction coefficient value of Zn^{II} revealed that 100 mg of bromate, carbonate, fluoride, iodate, iodide, nitrite, sulphide, thiocyanate, bromide, nitrate, perchlorate, hypophosphite, chromate, tartrate, acetate, dichromate, citrate, sulphite, thiosulphate and chloride; 50 mg of thiourea, sulphate and borate; 10 mg of tungstate and phosphate do not decrease the *E* value of Zn^{II}. Oxalate and EDTA lowered the *E* value of Zn^{II}. The interference was removed by decomposing with aqua regia prior to the extraction of Zn^{II}.

Of the cations studied, Sb^{III}, Na^I, Ce^{III}, Se^{IV}, Sb^V, Ir^{IV}, Cl^I, Rb^I, S^{VI} and Sn^{II} were extracted to the extent of less than 1.0%. P^V, W^{VI}, Sr^{II}, Re^{VII}, Ce^{IV}, Au^{III}, Mo^{VI}, As^{III}, Ba^{II}, Cr^{VI}, Ca^{II}, Cs^I and Ru^{III} were extracted between 1 and 10%. Tl^I, Hg^{II}, Ag^I, In^{III}, Cd^{II}, Sc^{III}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV}, La^{III} and Eu^{III} were extracted to more than 10%. The percentage extraction of Tl^I, Hg^{II}, Ag^I and Cd^{II} was reduced to 2.0, 0.4, 0.8, and 0.4% respectively with 100 mg of thiosulphate, that of Zr^{IV}, La^{III}, In^{III}, Sc^{III} and Eu^{III} was reduced to 0.5, 0.2, 0.4, 0.04 and 0.6% respectively by 100 mg of fluoride, and that of Co^{II} was lowered to 3% with 100 mg of thiocyanate. The extraction of Cr^{III} was reduced to 4% by oxidizing Cr^{III} to Cr^{VI} by boiling with NaOH and H₂O₂, whereas the extraction of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} was reduced to 1.4 and 1.2% respectively, by precipitating Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} as Fe(OH)₃ with NH₄Cl and NH₄OH after oxidizing Fe^{II} to Fe^{III} with HNO₃.

The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined by the method of sub-stoichiometric extraction. A plot of amount of Zn^{II} taken vs the activity of the organic aliquot gave a linear relationship until it was sub-equivalent to the reagent added, after which it remained constant. A break occurred at the stoichiometry of Zn^{II}: quinaldic acid in the ratio of 1:2. The stoichiometry of metal-to-reagent was further supported by the slope-ratio method and solid complex analysis.

1.0 mg of Zn^{II} was back-extracted to better than 99% with 20 ml of 1:1 HCl.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. grade. $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was used to prepare the stock solution of Zn^{II} . ^{65}Zn and the isotopes used for studying the cation interference were provided by B.R.I.T., Trombay. Solutions of the cations and anions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate salts in distilled water to give the desired concentration. Acid was added wherever necessary and these solutions were standardized³. Quinaldic acid was used as such.

The isotopes were counted such that β -emitters were counted on an end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, high voltage unit and a timer and γ -emitters were counted on a γ -ray spectrometer in conjunction with a 3.5 cm \times 3.5 cm. NaI(Tl) flat-type detector.

General extraction procedure : To a solution containing 1 mg of Zn^{II} labelled with ^{65}Zn , a 1% ethanolic solution of quinaldic acid (3 ml) was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 8.0 with ammonia solution and then equilibrated with benzyl alcohol (17 ml) for 4.0 min. Both the organic and the aqueous phase was allowed to separate. An aliquot (2-ml) of each phase was taken for counting on a γ -ray spectrometer at the channel corresponding to the 1.115 MeV photopeak of ^{65}Zn .

The stoichiometric ratio of Zn^{II} -to-reagent was determined by the method of sub-stoichiometric extraction which was carried out as follows. Increasing amount of Zn^{II} labelled with ^{65}Zn along with 12.8 mg of ethanolic solution of quinaldic acid was taken. The aqueous phase volume was made with distilled water. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 8.0 with ammonia solution and equilibrated for 4.0 min with 17 ml of benzyl alcohol. A 2-ml aliquot of the organic phase was counted on a γ -ray spectrometer at the channel corresponding to the 1.115 MeV photopeak of ^{65}Zn .

This separation procedure was applied for the radiochemical separation of Zn^{II} from neutron irradiated targets of environmental samples.

References

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